

Impact of Sociodemographic Factors on Screen Time Use Among Early Adolescents

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Adolescence is a formative period of life and the ideas developed in this period are usually carried over to life. The digital revolution and the COVID-19 pandemic have made the use of screens rampant and excessive. Thus, it is imperative to study screen time in adolescents.

Methods: This cross-sectional observational study was conducted among early adolescents(10-13 years) over a period of one year. After obtaining the ascent from children and informed consent from parents, the data was collected on a predesigned performa which included questions on demographic characteristics. By using the recall approach, information about screen time duration, content, and screen kinds (television, smartphones, computers, tablets, and video games) was gathered. The data were analyzed using SPSS software version 22. The p-value <0.05 was considered significant.

Results: The mean age of participants was 11.25 (1.11) years and the mean screen time was 144.24 (73.14) minutes. The male: female ratio was 1.74:1. A significant correlation was found between screen time and the place of living ($\chi^2 = 9.372$, p-value = 0.025), and the type of family ($\chi^2 = 39.157$, p-value <0.0001). No significant correlation was found between screen time and other demographic characteristics like age, gender, socioeconomic status, religion, maternal education, and maternal occupation.

Conclusion: The COVID-19 era has unleashed the effects of superfluous screen time on everybody. This new issue of the digital era, the rise in screen usage by adolescents, demands family, societal, and medical interventions.

Keywords: Adolescence, Demographic factors, Digital media, Screen usage.

INTRODUCTION

Adolescence is a remarkable period of human development and a crucial period for setting the pillars of good health, lasting from the age of 10 to 19 years. (1) Early adolescence is defined as the age group between 10-13 years. (2) Adolescents grow quickly in terms of their physical, cognitive, and emotional development which has an impact on their emotions, thoughts, decisions, and interactions with others and their environment. (3)

Screen time overuse is becoming a significant issue with the development of digital technology among children and adolescents. (4) According to recent research, watching screen media makes children and adolescents more likely to overeat as they watch, exposes them to high-calorie, low-nutrient foods and drinks that affect their preferences, requests for purchases, and consumption patterns, and shorten their sleep cycles. (5) The growth of physical and cognitive capacities has been linked unfavourably to screen time, particularly television viewing, whereas obesity, sleep issues, depression, and anxiety have been positively linked. (6)

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines recreational screen time as any time spent watching a screen (such as a computer, television (TV), or mobile device) for activities other than education/ study or work. (7) The WHO defines sedentary screen time as time spent engaging in screen-based entertainment (TV, computer, mobile devices), except interactive screen-based activities that demand movement or physical exercise. (7) The Australian Institute of Family Studies (AIFS) recommends that for children and young people aged 5-17 years, sedentary recreational screen time per day except for schoolwork should not be more than two hours. (8) The COVID-19 pandemic has seen an unprecedented rise in screen time as all educational, and recreational activities transferred to the digital mode. The Indian Academy of Pediatrics recommended up to one hour/per day for grades III to V, two hours/per day for grades VI to VIII, and three hours/per day for grades IX to XII for screen-based remote learning. (9) But a study showed that the actual screen time was much higher even for learning. (10)

It is important to assess screen time in adolescents as it has multiple health impacts on them. Thus, this study aimed to determine the average daily usage of screen time among the early adolescent age group as well as the relationship between screen time and demographic characteristics.

METHODS

This cross-sectional observational study was conducted at the Hind Institute of Medical Sciences, Uttar Pradesh among early adolescent age children over 1 year from February 2021 to January 2022. Early adolescent-age group children between 10-13 years of age, visiting the adolescent clinic of the Department of Pediatrics at Hind Institute of Medical Sciences were included in the study while those children with any type of chronic illness, physical or mental impairment, and visual or auditory impairment were excluded.

After obtaining the ascent from children and informed consent from parents, the data was collected on a predesigned performa which included questions on demographic characteristics i.e., age, gender, livelihood, socioeconomic status, religion, maternal education, maternal occupation, family type, and screen time per day. By using the recall approach, information about screen time duration, content, and screen kinds (TV, smartphones, computers, tablets, and video games) was gathered. The period of screen time on a normal school day and a normal holiday was compiled, and the average amount of time spent on screens every day over the course of a week was computed.

The data were analyzed using SPSS software version 22. Descriptive statistics were used to compute demographic characteristics. The Chi-square test was used to find a correlation between demographic characteristics and screen time usage. The p-value <0.05 was considered significant.

RESULTS

A total of 408 early adolescent-age children participated in the study. The mean age of participants was 11.25 (1.11) years and the mean screen time was 144.24 (73.14) minutes. The demographic characteristics of participants are represented in Table 1.

Table 1: The demographic characteristics of participants (n=408)

Parameter	Number of participants (n)	Percentage (%)
Age in years		
10	140	34.3
11	98	24
12	99	24.3
13	71	17.4
Gender		
Male	259	63.5
Female	149	36.5
Livelihood		
Rural	234	57.4
Urban	174	42.6
Socioeconomic status		
Upper	11	2.7
Upper middle	78	19.1
Middle	126	30.9
Upper lower	112	27.4
Lower	81	19.9
Religion		
Hindu	240	58.8
Muslim	114	27.9
Others	54	13.3
Maternal education		
Illiterate	14	3.4
Primary school	96	23.5
High School	106	26
Intermediate	138	33.8

<i>Graduate</i>	39	9.6
<i>>=Post-graduate</i>	15	3.7
Maternal Occupation		
<i>Unemployed</i>	257	63
<i>Employed</i>	151	37
Family type		
<i>Nuclear</i>	263	64.5
<i>Joint</i>	145	35.5
Screen time per day		
<i><60 minutes</i>	30	7.4
<i>60 - <120 minutes</i>	160	39.2
<i>120 - <180 minutes</i>	86	21.1
<i>≥180 minutes</i>	132	32.3

Among the participants, 259 (63.5%) were males, and 174 (42.6%) resided in urban areas. The majority of participants belong to the middle (30.9%) and upper-lower classes (27.4%). Most of the participants followed Hinduism (58.8%). Most of the mothers were educated above primary school (73.1%) and were unemployed (63%). The majority belong to nuclear families (64.5%). The number of participants with <60, 60 - <120, 120 - <180, and ≥180 minutes screen time per day were 30 (7.4%), 160 (39.2%), 86 (21.1%), and 132 (32.3%) respectively. The relationship between screen time and the demographic characteristics of participants is represented in Table 2.

Table 2: The Correlation between screen time and demographic characteristics of participants (n=408)

Parameter	Number of Participants (n)				Chi-square test value	p-value
	<60	60 - <120	120 - <180	≥180		
Age in years						
<i>10</i>	9	62	29	40	4.746	0.856
<i>11</i>	8	35	18	37		
<i>12</i>	8	35	25	31		
<i>13</i>	5	28	14	24		
Gender					0.074	0.995
<i>Male</i>	19	101	54	85		
<i>Female</i>	11	59	32	47		
Livelihood					9.372	0.025*
<i>Rural</i>	24	89	42	79		
<i>Urban</i>	6	71	44	53		
Socioeconomic status					6.874	0.866
<i>Upper</i>	0	7	1	3		
<i>Upper middle</i>	6	27	17	28		
<i>Middle</i>	8	47	32	39		
<i>Upper lower</i>	9	44	22	37		
<i>Lower</i>	7	35	14	25		
Religion					4.604	0.596
<i>Hindu</i>	19	88	48	85		
<i>Muslim</i>	9	47	27	31		
<i>Others</i>	2	25	11	16		
Maternal education						
<i>Illiterate</i>	0	6	2	6		
<i>Primary school</i>	5	41	20	30		

<i>High School</i>	10	39	23	34	9.424	0.854
<i>Intermediate</i>	12	57	29	40		
<i>Graduate</i>	2	10	9	18		
<i>>=Post-graduate</i>	1	7	3	4		
Maternal Occupation						
<i>Unemployed</i>	17	101	59	80	2.001	0.572
<i>Employed</i>	13	59	27	52		
Family type						
<i>Nuclear</i>	30	80	68	85	39.157	<0.0001*
<i>Joint</i>	0	80	18	47		

*Significant p-value <0.05.

Screen time was significantly related to the place of living and type of family. No significant relation was found between the rest of the demographic characteristics and screen time.

DISCUSSION

The World Health Organization recommends that children and adolescents (aged 5-17 years) should reduce their sedentary time, particularly their recreational screen time. (7) This study focused to determine the average daily screen time usage among the early adolescent age group and the relationship between their screen time usage and demographic characteristics.

In the present study, most of the children were of 10 years of age (34.3%) but there was no significant correlation between screen time use and the age of children (p-value 0.856). This was in accordance with a study by Shirley et al which reported no significant correlation between age and screen time duration. (11) There was no significant correlation between screen time use and the gender of children in our study (p-value 0.995). In contrast, Nagata et al. reported in their study that there was a higher screen time usage in males (0.75 hours more) than in females. (12)

In the present study, there was a significant positive correlation between screen time use and place of living. In contrast, a study by Varadarajan et al reported no significant correlation between excessive screen time use and area of residence (rural/urban). (13) There was no significant correlation between screen time use and socioeconomic status, religion, maternal education, and maternal occupation in the present study. Similar to our study, Varadarajan et al did not report any significant correlation between excessive screen time use with either socioeconomic status or with maternal education level. (13) Dubey et al also found no significant association between socioeconomic status and screen time use by adolescents. (14) Likewise, Shirley et al. did not report any significant correlation between excessive screen time use with maternal occupation. (11)

A highly significant positive correlation was reported between family type and excessive screen time use (p-value <0.0001) in our study. Shwetha et al also reported similar findings in their study. (15) In contrast to our study, Varadarajan et al did not report any significant correlation between excessive screen time use with the type of family. (13)

According to the Indian Academy of Pediatrics (IAP), children aged 5 to 10 years should limit their daily screen usage to no more than two hours—the fewer, the better. (16) For adolescents aged 10-18 years, IAP recommends that screen time should be moderated with other pursuits that are essential to overall development which includes at least an hour of playing outside, 8 to 9 hours of sleep at night, as well as time for homework, meals, hobbies, social contact, and family time. Screen time has to be suitably lowered to make room for any activities that are compromised as a result of the aforementioned ones. (16)

One of the limitations of this study was that it was conducted at a single centre only, so generalization of results may not be possible. Further studies are recommended involving a multicentric approach.

CONCLUSION

A key impending issue of the digital era is the rise in screen time among young children and early adolescents, which has been linked to detrimental effects on physical, mental, and social development. Social action must be made to raise parents' knowledge of the negative effects of excessive screen time on teenagers and to stress the need of following the recommendations. The COVID-19 pandemic has revealed the harmful effects of excessive media usage. To address this increasing issue, interventions are needed at the family, school, social, health care, national, and international levels.

DECLARATIONS

Ethical approval: Approval taken by the Institute Ethics Committee.

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FINANCIAL SUPPORT & SPONSORSHIP

NIL

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DISCLOSURE

There is no conflict of interest to be declared by the authors.

REFERENCES

1. Adolescent health. **WHO**. [Accessed 2022 Sep 24]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/health-topics/adolescent-health>
2. **Rathoria E, Rathoria R, Bansal U, Agarwal A**. Prevalence of overweight and obesity in adolescents from eastern Uttar Pradesh. *Int J Sci Res*. 2021;10(1):49-51. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6681668>
3. Adolescents. **Mdpi.com**. [Accessed 2022 Sep 24]. Available from: <https://www.mdpi.com/journal/adolescents/about>
4. **Pandya A, Lodha P**. Social connectedness, excessive screen time during COVID-19 and mental health: a review of current evidence. *Frontiers in Human Dynamics*. 2021 Jul 22;3. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fhumd.2021.684137>
5. **Robinson TN, Banda JA, Hale L, Lu AS, Fleming-Milici F, Calvert SL, Wartella E**. Screen media exposure and obesity in children and adolescents. *Pediatrics*. 2017 Nov;140(Supplement 2):S97-101. <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2016-1758K>
6. Domingues-Montanari S. Clinical and psychological effects of excessive screen time on children. *Journal of paediatrics and child health*. 2017 Apr;53(4):333-8. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jpc.13462>
7. WHO guidelines on physical activity and sedentary behaviour. World Health Organization; 2020 [Accessed 2022 Sep 24]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240015128>
8. Too much time on screens? Screen time effects and guidelines for children and young people. The Australian Institute of Family Studies. [Accessed 2022 Sep 24]. Available from: <https://aifs.gov.au/resources/short-articles/too-much-time-screens-screen-time-effects-and-guidelines-children-and>
9. **Ghate S, Parekh BJ, Thapar RK, Nadkarni PR, Sen S, Bansal U, Sambhariya CH, Popat S, Bhattacharya P, Kirtani S, Kanetkar Y, Vats SP, Kamath SS, Raj M, Basavaraja GV, Gupta P**. Indian Academy of Pediatrics Guidelines on School Reopening, Remote Learning and Curriculum in and After the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Indian Pediatr*. 2020 Dec 15;57(12):1153-1165. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13312-020-2072-7>
10. **Bansal U, Ghate S, Bhattacharya P, Thapar RK, Gupta P**. Parental Perspectives on Remote Learning and School Reopening. *Indian Pediatr*. 2020 Dec 15;57(12):1177-1178. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13312-020-2075-4>
11. **Alph Shirley S, Santha Kumar S**. A study on screen time use in children between 24 to 60 months of age in Tamil Nadu, India. *Int J Contemp Pediatr*. 2019;6(6):2582-6. Available from: <https://ijpediatrics.com/index.php/ijcp/article/view/2903/1973>
12. **Nagata JM, Ganson KT, Iyer P, Chu J, Baker FC, Gabriel KP, Garber AK, Murray SB, Bibbins-Domingo K**. Sociodemographic Correlates of Contemporary Screen Time Use among 9-and 10-Year-Old Children. *The Journal of Pediatrics*. 2022 Jan 1;240:213-20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpeds.2021.08.077>
13. **Varadarajan S, Govindarajan Venguidesvarane A, Ramaswamy KN, Rajamohan M, Krupa M, Winfred Christadoss SB**. Prevalence of excessive screen time and its association with developmental delay in children aged < 5 years: A population-based cross-sectional study in India. *Plos one*. 2021 Jul 6;16(7):e0254102. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0254102>
14. **Dubey M, Nongkynrih B, Gupta SK, Kalaivani M, Goswami AK, Salve HR**. Screen-based media use and screen time assessment among adolescents residing in an Urban Resettlement Colony in New Delhi, India. *Journal of family medicine and primary care*. 2018 Nov;7(6):1236. https://doi.org/10.4103/jfmpe.jfmpe_190_18
15. **Shwetha G, Doddaiiah SK, Bilimale AS, Murthy MN**. Assessing the usage of screen based media and screen time among adolescents in Mysuru: a cross-sectional study. *International Journal of Community Medicine and Public Health*. 2020 Jun;7(6):2233. <https://doi.org/10.18203/2394-6040.ijcmph20202477>
16. **Gupta P, Shah D, Bedi N, Galagali P, Dalwai S, Agrawal S, John JJ, Mahajan V, Meena P, Mittal HG, Narmada S**. Indian Academy of Pediatrics Guidelines on Screen Time and Digital Wellness in Infants, Children and Adolescents. *Indian Pediatr*. 2022 Mar;59(3):235-44. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13312-022-2477-6>

THYROID : YEAR IN REVIEW

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Thyroid disorders in children are very common endocrinal issues. Still for some disorders we are searching for the most suitable management. This Year review will help the readers to keep abreast about current research & potential therapy to come in future.

1-Associations between maternal urinary iodine assessment, dietary iodine intakes and neurodevelopmental outcomes in the child: a systematic review *Monaghan et al. Thyroid Research (2021) 14:14*
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13044-021-00105->

Using PRISMA guidelines, a comprehensive search was conducted in three electronic databases (EMBASE®, MedLine® and Web of Science®) from January 1970–March 2021

- **Conclusion:** The majority of studies classified pregnant women to be mild-moderately iodine deficient based on urinary iodine assessment (UIC and/or ICr) and/or dietary intakes, with subsequent offspring neurodevelopment implications identified. This review suggests that dietary intake data may indicate a stronger association with cognitive outcomes than urinary iodine measurements alone.
- The strength of this review distinguishes results based on cognitive outcome per urinary iodine assessment strategy (UIC and/or ICr) with dietary data.

Future work is needed respecting the usefulness of urinary iodine assessment (UIC and/or ICr) as an indicator of deficiency whilst also taking account of dietary intakes.

2- Metformin reverses Hashimoto's Thyroiditis by regulating Immune key Events

- *Frontiers in developmental & cell biology May 2021,*
- **Background:** Hashimoto's thyroiditis (HT) is a common autoimmune disease characterized by high levels of thyroid peroxidase antibody (TPOAb) and thyroid globulin antibody (TgAb) as well as infiltration of lymphocytes in thyroid.
- In recent years, metformin has been proven to be effective in a variety of autoimmune diseases, such as systemic lupus erythematosus, rheumatoid arthritis and multiple sclerosis.
- **Methods:** This study systematically explored the therapeutic effect of metformin on HT and its underlying mechanism by comprehensively utilizing methods including animal model, in vitro cell culture and differentiation, mRNA sequencing and 16S rRNA sequencing.
- **Findings:** metformin indeed had a therapeutic effect on mice with HT mainly by reducing TgAb and lymphocyte infiltration in thyroid tissue.
- In addition, metformin also significantly suppressed the number and function of Th17 cells and M1 macrophages polarization in HT mice.
- The results of mRNA sequencing of thyroid tissue illustrated that the therapeutic effect of metformin on HT was mainly achieved by **regulating immune pathways**.

3- Effect of Micronutrients on Thyroid Parameters

- *Journal of Thyroid Research Volume 2021, Hari Krishnan Krishnamurthy, USA*
- Micronutrients are involved in various vital cellular metabolic processes including thyroid hormone metabolism.
- **correlation between serum levels of micronutrients and their effects on thyroid parameters.**
- correlation of serum levels of micronutrients and thyroid markers was studied in a group of healthy individuals tested for thyroid markers (T4, T3, FT4, FT3, TSH, anti-TPO, RT3, and anti-Tg) and their micronutrient profile at Vibrant America Clinical Laboratory
- subjects were rationalized into three groups (deficient, normal, or excess levels of micronutrients), and the levels of their thyroid markers were compared.
- results, **deficiency of vitamin B2, B12, B9 and Vit-D25[OH] (p < 0.05) significantly affected thyroid functioning.**
- Other elemental micronutrients such as calcium, copper, choline, iron, and zinc (p < 0.05) have a significant correlation with serum levels of free T3.